

Organizational Triggers in Managing Employee Performance Quality in Georgian Organizations

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ABSTRACT: Our environment has feedback as a trigger. After all, our environment constantly gives us new information important to our lives and changes our behavior. Triggers are often some sort of internal or external stimulus that causes the former addict and are reminders that put people in emotional and mental place of pain, anger, distress, frustration and other strong emotions. Therefore, it is important for managers in organizations not only to help workers control emotional situations but be able to control their own feelings, which can help contribute to a healthy environment, allow workers to perform according to their potential and maintain workers' morale. The paper is about qualitative research in two Georgian organizations. It was interesting which organizational triggers were used in these companies and how these triggers were used by managers for improving the performance quality of service employees, therefore interviews were conducted with the people who were involved in managing people.

KEYWORDS: organizational triggers, performance quality, service employees

Introduction

A trigger is something that performs a specific action. Also, any stimulus that shapes our thoughts and actions can appear suddenly and it can be major or minor moments, pleasant or ambitious. Our environment is the most powerful mechanism of use in our lives, which does not always work in our favor, we make plans to achieve our goals, but the environment is constantly interfering. It is always interesting which organizational triggers have place in organizations and the effect of these triggers on employee performance.

Organizational Triggers

A specific action is performed by a trigger. Also, any stimulus that shapes our thoughts and actions can appear suddenly and it can be major or minor moments, pleasant or ambitious. Our environment is the most powerful mechanism of use in our lives, which does not always work in our favor, we make plans to achieve our goals, but the environment is constantly interfering.

I want to mention two deep researchers on the triggers in psychology: Robert Cialdini and Marshall Goldsmith. If we want to achieve that, at first, we must define the term trigger. Marshall Goldsmith defined trigger as a stimulus that impacts our behaviour (Goldsmith 2007). Cialdini believes that money, time, and our lives can manipulate us if we are not careful. To protect yourself, one way is to be aware of all the tricks that people use to convince us. For this, Cialdini earned a reputation as a "master of influence".

There are six triggers described by Cialdini as the main drivers to influence others:

- **Reciprocity-** It is deeply ingrained psychological trigger. When we act in favour of another person, they have also an obligation to return, which means - benefits for benefits. Much greater feedback can be led by the initial small kindness.
- **Scarcity-** Something is difficult to achieve when there is a shortage of resources or the faster, we want to achieve it. Shortly it's - scarcity. When society does not have

enough productive resources to meet all needs, it is scarcity, from an academic point of view.

- Consistency and Commitment – these two are operated on two levels. For the future behaviour, the best predictor is its past, this is the first level. People try to conform to previous actions and thoughts. Therefore, when the goal is publicly announced, making significant changes in lifestyle becomes much more successful. Second, the premise of great consent is small consent, which means that the first "yes" to face-to-face sales is simpler than the next.
- Authority- This is one of the scariest psychological triggers. Authority takes a principled step to use the power of particular individuals, where social evidence is based on popular power - i.e., people "just like me". Authority is dangerous because it has power. According to Cialdini, there is a tendency that the action can be repeated in response to simple symbols rather than its essence. The most effective symbol can be automobiles and clothe, this is shown by the research. In other words, people react also to authority's appearance.
- Liking - Another obvious trigger that is not at all easy. No matter how logical our decisions may be, in reality "people prefer to give their yes to those who know and like them." To say in short, when they like you, they will buy from you. Approval can be expressed in both: common interests and similarities and physical attractiveness.
- Social proof – The crowd is a powerful force, whether we like to admit it or not. If we consider sales, then we can understand this easily. To increase sales, the first psychological trigger must come from people who are already using the product or service and not from us.

Triggers are positive and negative. The negative triggers can cause the most damaging effects. Common triggers may lead to depression, frustration, isolation, broken relationships, and in some cases, it may lead to suicide.

When individuals are triggered, spiralling into various compulsions and behaviours, irritability, guilt, low self-esteem and anger can surface. Emotional and mental triggers can be traumatizing and run very deep. Individuals may push to adopt unhealthy ways of coping, such as harm to others, self-harm, and substance abuse.

Triggers in the workplace context

People should learn in order for organizations to learn. Individuals carry out what's expected of them, each written and unwritten expectations. Written expectations are usually delivered through job descriptions, memos, e-mails, and official documents. What's less clear for people within a structure are the unwritten expectations. For understanding unwritten expectations, three groupings in organizations, according to Maira and Scott-Morgan (1997) are: triggers, motivators and enablers.

Triggers, or triggering events, are outlined as circumstances that act as catalysts to structure learning. Like persons, organizations don't learn proactively (Watkins and Marsick 1993). Given the tremendous pressures to perform and turn out results, organizations tend to over-invest in exploiting existing data and under-invest in learning or developing new data (Levinthal 1991).

Workplace is a stressful environment, which involves many situations and for that reason it may trigger strong negative feelings. It is important for managers not only to help workers control emotional situations but be able to control their own feelings. This can help contribute to a healthy environment, allow workers to perform according to their potential and maintain workers' morale. It is important for most stressful situations that manager is able to respond in a rational, calm and positive manner. This helps encourage workers to see the situation more objectively. In contrast, when managers add their own emotions into the mix, it

can be very unhelpful for fueling workers' emotions. When they react in unhelpful ways, managers can send the message to workers that they can lead the team through hard times and are incapable of remaining calm. When managers have the ability to resolve an emotionally charged problem and demonstrate empathy, it can give workers confidence and that competent and strong leaders oversee these workers.

Qualitative research

Qualitative methodologies are used to evaluate and analyze non-numerical information. These methods are applicable to studies that involve relationships between individuals, individuals and their environments, and motives that drive individual action and behavior. According to Berrios and Lucca (2006) qualitative methods provide for a "better understanding of human development" and according to Gerdes and Conn (2001) qualitative methods allow looking at the "whole rather than the parts". Because qualitative research method process emerges from patterns found in the data, these methods permit flexibility and procedure change.

At first, in order to gain some information about organizational triggers in Georgian organizations, I decided to make interview the people involved in managing people. Their opinion was interesting and important about organizational triggers. I was interested which organizational triggers were used in these companies and how these triggers were used by managers for improving the performance quality of service employees.

For the interviews, I selected managers from two organizations that were associated with education. One was public organization – EMIS (Education Management Information System) and second – private – ELL (English Language and Life). The number of samples was – 18 respondents. I will briefly introduce the mentioned companies.

Education Management Information System (EMIS) was established in 2012.

The mission of the management system is to provide the education system with advanced technologies and electronic resources for the best education and management.

The strategy of the Education Management Information System is to promote the functioning of the Ministry of Education and Science in the educational space through the introduction of modern information and communication technologies.

LEPL - Education Management Information System objectives:

In order to fulfill the mission, the goal of the management system in the education system of Georgia is:

- Development of information and communication technologies and ensuring their accessibility in the learning process;
- Development of management information systems;
- Providing information on decision-making processes;
- Production and dissemination of educational statistics.

In 2002 in Tbilisi, Educational Agency ELL was established.

At that time ELL was the first educational agency in the Georgian market and today they are already considered one of the most experienced and professional agencies, with a good reputation and excellent recommendations from their clients and educational institutions.

In 2015, the ELL English Language Center was recognized as the best language center in Georgia by the Cambridge English Language Assessment, preparing students for the Cambridge International Examinations and awarding them the relevant qualification certificate.

In addition, the ELL English Language Center is the holder of the UK Council's Advantage Gold Program as the best student preparation center for the Cambridge exams.

18 interviews were conducted, 11 of them in the Education Management Information System (EMIS) and 7 in English Language and Life (ELL). Respondents who participated

were representatives of the management of these companies, because I was interested in the impact of triggers on employees whose quality of work was then reflected in the provided services.

Table 1. Demographic Data of Respondents

Number of Respondents	18
Position	Managers
Gender	12 women, 6 men
Age	31 average

Source: own research

When I started the interview process by asking what they thought and tell briefly about the organization where they worked, I was pleasantly surprised when all twenty of them evaluated the companies almost similarly and positively. It was noted that this was a place where they were able to freely use their abilities, talents, implement ideas, as it was the leaders who helped. The answer of the sixth interviewer was: "This is an institution that does a great job for the country, for the education system, for the students, for the universities. I am happy to work here because I know every job, I do is a step forward in both my career and the country's education system."

When asked which performance appraisal method was used by them, some respondents indicated that they and employees together identify, plan, organize and communicate objectives and after setting clear goals, they periodically discuss the progress made to control and have conversation on the feasibility of achieving those set objectives. This appraisal method is called Management by objectives (MBO), it is a process where the goals of the organization are defined and management conveys it to employees with the intention to achieve each objective.

Some of the respondents noticed that they have also self-evaluation assessment, where employees conduct their performance assessment firstly on their own against a set list of criteria. This appraisal method is called self-evaluation. The fourth respondent replied: "At the end of each quarter, we have developed a self-assessment report which compares the employee's work with the pre-defined work. When each employee fills out a form, management will analyze the work which is done and not done, after which changes will be made, if it is necessary."

Most of the respondents mentioned that the performance appraisal of the employees was best done by the customer. Accordingly, they rated performance when listening to customer reviews. This appraisal method is called 360-degree feedback, where review includes not just the direct feedback from the manager, but also from other sources.

The answer of the ninth respondent: "It is very nice when the customer, in this case a student or an educational institution, hears that the issue is completed on time and with quality, when they are satisfied with the work done by the staff and when the work done helps them a lot. Do you know? There was an accident, when minutes interrupt too much in a student's life and there is nothing more enjoyable than seeing the student's lightened eyes and the cause of which is precisely the timely performance of your employee."

As for questions about performance indicators, which indicators were key in their organization, respondents' opinions were divided. The results were distributed as follows:

Figure 1. Key performance indicators in their organizations

Customer satisfaction was mentioned by almost all of them. When you provide services to students, educational institutions, they think it is necessary to measure their level of satisfaction as well. In their view performance indicators can also be the average time it takes to respond to customers, the number of customer issues and the average number of issues that is difficult for employee to solve.

When respondents named the triggers that were implemented in their organization, I asked the nominees to select the ones that had the greatest impact on employees.

The result looks like this:

Figure 2. "Organizational triggers" which have the greatest impact on employees

When people have made a voluntary public and written commitment to doing so, they are more likely to embrace a proposal. Respondents think consistency and commitment has the biggest impact on employees. One of them noted: "During meetings, when an assignment is publicly issued to each employee and a public commitment is made to complete it on time, it all has the greatest impact on him and the work done. The reason is the responsibility that arose after making a public commitment".

Typically, new executives are a sign of wide-ranging changes in the organization. They are ready to meet with employees, for wide discussions, are purposeful, try to solve existing gaps or problems, are looking to prove their value quickly and they are more open to fresh ideas. Accordingly, each employee tries to influence them as much as possible and do their

best. Introducing a new service in the company requires more effort from employees as the number of jobs increases, the execution time does not change, the customer becomes more demanding. Consequently each employee becomes more motivated to live up to management hopes. Any kind of reward should somehow make a person more motivated. Raises self-esteem, is satisfied with the work done and tries to get the same in the future.

Employers are promoting self-efficacy among staff, when they provide employee recognition at the organizational level. Similarly, employers are promoting employee motivation, when they support the value of work at the individual level.

Respondents from both companies noted that since each of them is unique, the management used an individually selected form of incentive because they were confident that the selected reward would be significant to a particular employee.

The stimulus unanimously mentioned by respondents from both companies was the promotion opportunities. The reason is clear, when employees are provided by opportunities for the growth and advancement, they feel contented and satisfied and become more committed to the organization. The next stimuli which was mentioned was job enrichment, when employers increase employees’ responsibilities by giving them an important designation. Other stimuli were: providing positive feedback for quality work, competitive salary, bonuses, paid seek and parental leave, quality health insurance, flexibility to work at home, staff celebrations, desirable office space and work equipment.

Table 2. Stimuli that is used for better performance in organizations

EMIS:	ELL:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion opportunities • Job enrichment • Positive feedback for quality work • Competitive salary • Paid seek and parental leave • Flexibility to work at home • Staff celebrations • Quality health insurance • Desirable office space • Desirable work equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job enrichment • Bonuses • Staff celebrations • Quality health insurance • Desirable office space • Desirable work equipment

Source: own research

Conclusion

By focusing on the development of employees and the alignment of company goals, managers can create a work environment that enables both employees and companies to thrive. In any organization, it's important to understand what your employees are doing, why they are doing and how they are doing it. When there is no system in place to define roles, provide constructive feedback, understand individual strengths and weaknesses, trigger interventions and reward positive behavior, it is much more difficult for managers to effectively lead their employees.

The article clearly shows the importance of organizational triggers for employees and that each trigger has a fairly large impact on the quality of their performance. Consequently, this issue should be the subject of frequent observations by management, as each incorrect trigger can dramatically drop the quality of performance and consequently have a major impact on the company in the end.

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